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STUDY METHODOLOGY OF ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY IN SiS:Er MONOCRYSTAL

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12103891>

ANNOTATION

The study of the change of electrical conductivity of SiS:Er monocrystals depending on the voltage determined the presence of electroluminescence additive centers, their penetration depth, the width of the forbidden zone, and other parameters characterizing their electrophysical properties.

Key words: single crystal, electrical conductivity, additive conductivity, lanthanoids, potential barrier, donor level

The rapid development of science and technology in modern times increases the demand for multifunctional semiconductor materials. In recent decades, the experimental production of graphene and the study of nanoscale thin films have increased the interest in layered crystals. When the issue is approached from this context, SiS, which is the object of research, and its SiS:Er layered single crystals doped with Er atoms can be considered as a relevant semiconductor substance.

Not only the SiS crystal, but also other silicon monochalcogenides can be used in the optical and holographic recording of information, in the preparation of polarized radiation photoanalyzers, and in the manufacture of electric switches.

Silicon monosulfide is a strongly anisotropic layered crystal with a high concentration of structural vacancies and is characterized by high photosensitivity in the near-infrared region of the spectrum. Defects caused by vacancies in SiS single crystals lead to phenomena of practical interest, such as memory overshoot effect of residual conductivity, optoelectronic memory. In order to correctly understand the main essence of the indicated phenomena, it is necessary to determine the shape of the absorption boundary of the studied crystals, to determine its fine structure, to obtain the necessary information about the defects, additives, free charges and oscillations of the crystal lattice.

Conducting optical studies within the absorption band and in the transparency region and examining the obtained results based on the appropriate theory provides an opportunity to obtain

complete information about the energy zone structure of substances. In general, the optical properties of semiconductors mean the interaction of photons with electrons and atoms in the crystal. This effect is the basis of various transformations of absorption, modulation and the generation of illumination, and is also the basis of optoelectronics.

The study of the change of electrical conductivity of SiS:Er monocrystals depending on the voltage determined the presence of electroluminescence additive centers, their penetration depth, the width of the forbidden zone, and other parameters characterizing their electrophysical properties.

The study of electrical conductivity provides information on the mechanism of conductivity change, electroluminescence, the presence of dopant centers and their penetration depth, the width of the forbidden zone, and other parameters characterizing the electrophysical properties of semiconductors. 1x3x100 mm³ rectangular parallelepiped-shaped oriented samples were used to measure electrical conductivity. The samples are arranged so that the longest blade of the parallelepiped is directed in the direction of the $\vec{a}$ or $\vec{b}$ crystallographic axes, and the shortest blade is directed in the direction of the $\vec{c}$ axis.

Temperature dependence of electrical conductivity 10-3 mm. c.st. pressure was studied in the temperature range of 100 ÷ 500 K. Serious anisotropy of electrical conductivity was observed in all studied samples.

Figure 1 shows the temperature dependence of the dark conductivity of SiS single crystals in different directions in Arrhenius coordinates $\lg\sigma \sim f(1/T)$. Studies show that the conductivity in the $E \parallel \vec{c}$ direction in SiS single crystals is at least two orders of magnitude smaller than the conductivity in the $E \parallel \vec{a}$ and $E \parallel \vec{b}$ directions. From the temperature dependence of additive conductivity, the existence of $E_v + 0.42$ eV donor level in the forbidden zone of SiS single crystals was revealed.

In the region of additional conductivity, the tendency of the temperature dependence of electrical conductivity in the direction of the $\vec{c}$ axis is greater than in the directions perpendicular to that axis. This fact is explained by the presence of energy barriers for layers in SiS single crystals in directions parallel to the $\vec{a}$ axis.

Erbium-doped SiS:Er single crystals, unlike pure SiS single crystals, have a dopant depletion region in the temperature range 270 K < T < 350 K (Figure 2).

In the low temperature region (140÷270K), the electrical conductivity of single crystals is weakly dependent on temperature. Experiments conducted in parallel with ours show that the electrical conductivity decreases as the percentage of additives increases up to 0.1%. The further increase of the amount of Er additive up to 0.1%÷1% leads to an increase in electrical conductivity.

Figure 1. SiS single crystal electrical conductivity

In the temperature interval $T < 250$ K, the electrical conductivity is related to the fact that charge carriers in localized states close to the Fermi level become delocalized in the conduction zone as a result of thermal excitation.

Figure 2. Temperature dependence of electrical conductivity of SiS and SiS:Er single crystals 1–SiS; 2–SiS:E

LITERATURE:

1. Liu Tsun-Hua, Pashinkin A.S., Novoselova A.V. Research on the silicon-sulfur system. DAN USSR, 1963, T. 151, No. 6, C. 1335-1338.

2. Bletskan D.I., Bodnar F.V., Potoriy M.V., Chepur D.V. Obtaining monocrystals of dichalcogenides of silicon and tin and studying their properties. // В кн.: Тезисы прополов II Vsesoyuznoy konferencie po rostu kristallov, Kharkiv, 1982, Ch. 2, C. 25.

3. Rajesh K.U., Yi-Ying L., Chia-Yung K., Srinivasa R.T., Raman S., Karunakara M.B., Ankur A. High Photosensitivity and Broad Spectral Response of Multi-Layered Silicon Sulfide Transistors. // Nanoscale, 2016, V.8, p.2284-2292.

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